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***In Vitro* Study Of Indirect Mechanism of Plant Growth Promotion**

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ABSTRACT

Nine isolates of soil bacteria were tested in vitro. Parameters assessed were HCN production, volatile compound production, production of non-volatile diffusible metabolite, protease enzyme production, antagonistic effect on phytopathogen. HCN production was tested qualitatively by picric acid and ammonium carbonate reagent and antagonistic activity is tested against stem rot causing pathogen *sclerotium A. niger* and *A. flavus* by dual culture technique. None of the culture showed HCN production and volatile compound production activity. Six cultures isolates NM/S3/NA, NM/S4/NA, NM/S6/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/R2/RA NM/R3/RA showed protease production All cultures showed production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on phytopathogen *A. niger* whereas none of the bacterial isolates showed production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on phytopathogen *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium*. After three days of inoculation. The effect diluted after third day. Maximum inhibition showed by NM/S3/NA and minimum inhibition showed by NM/S1/CA and NM/S8/CA. Antagonistic activity is shown by culture NM/R3/RA against phytopathogen *A. niger* whilecultures NM/S4/NA, NM/S5/NA, NM/R2/RA showed minimum antagonistic activity as they are touching to the culture against phytopathogen *A. flavus*. None of the culture showed antagonistic activity against *Sclerotium*.

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Introduction

The microbe-plant interaction in the rhizosphere can be beneficial, neutral, variable or deleterious for plant. According to Kloepper (1) Rhizobacteria that can exert beneficial affects on plant development are termed plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR). Subbarao, (2) term rhizobacteria is used for bacteria that aggressively colonize the rhizosphere. It is evidence from the previous studies conducted in different laboratories that rhizobacteria are attached to seed and root exudates by chemotaxis which rightly said as first step in seed and root colonization.

Cattelan *et al.*, (3) stated that, although the mechanisms by which PGPR promote plant growth are not yet fully understood, many different traits of these bacteria are responsible for growth promotion activities. Glick *et al.*, (4) stated that, Initially Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria enhance plant growth by direct or indirect mechanisms. According to Weller and Cook (5); Dunne *et al.*, (6)

The indirect mechanism of plant growth promotion by PGPR include i) HCN production ii) volatile compound production iii) production of non-volatile diffusible metabolite production. iv) Production of protease enzyme v) antagonistic effect on phytopathogen.

This study was aimed to assess the potential of nine soil bacteria isolates in producing plant growth promotion by indirect method i.e., HCN production, volatile metabolite production, production of non-volatile diffusible metabolite, protease enzyme production and antagonistic effect on phytopathogen.

Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used for the present research work were procured from Glaxo, Mumbai and Hi Media Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai. The glasswares used were of Borosil make and were cleaned with 6 N HCl, rinsed with distilled water and oven dried before use.

Bacterial isolates NM/S1/CA, NM/S3/NA, NM/S4/NA, NM/S5/NA, NM/S6/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/S8/CA, NM/R2/RA, NM/R3/RA were isolated from rhizospheric soil of the soybean and were tested for potential for producing plant growth promoting attributes by indirect method i.e., HCN production, volatile metabolite production, production of non-volatile diffusible metabolite, protease enzyme production, antagonistic effect on phytopathogen.

1 HCN Production

Vasudevan *et al.*, (7); Mathivanan *et al.*, (8) stated in the research article that Production of Hydrogen cyanide is supposed to contribute to the biological suppression of soil plant pathogen most efficiently. Production of HCN by isolates was determined as per Lorck (9) Bacterial isolates were inoculated in different test tubes with Kings B Medium amended with glycine 4.4 gm/l. Whatman's filter paper stripes soaked in solution of 0.5% picric acid and 2% ammonium carbonate were immersed in each of the test tubes in such a manner that the strip remain suspended in the test tube without touching the media.

The HCN produced reacts with picric acid in the presence of ammonium carbonate $[(NH_4)_2CO_3]$ to give orange colour. Negative reaction shows no colour change, i.e. the yellow colour of the substrate remains unchanged.

2 Production of volatile metabolite

For testing the ability of the bacterial isolates for production of the volatile metabolite having inhibitory effect on phytopathogen. The Kings-B agar plates were prepared and under aseptic condition a mycelial disc of 8mm, from four days old sporulated pure culture of respective fungal were placed in the center of Petri dish. Bacterial test culture was inoculated center of another Petri dish. These two bases of Petri plates were placed face to face preventing any physical contact between the pathogen and the bacterial culture, and were sealed with paraffin wax and cellophane tape to isolate the inside atmosphere and to prevent loss of volatile formed. Plates were incubated for 48 hrs at $28 \pm 2^\circ C$ along with negative control. Results were observed after every 24 hrs in term of growth of phytopathogen on Kings-B medium in both test and the negative control and % inhibition was calculated. Using the following formula by Montealegro *et al.*, (10)

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = (1 - (\text{fungal growth} / \text{Control growth}) \times 100$$

3. Production of non-volatile diffusible metabolite

For testing the ability of the bacterial isolates for production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on tested phytopathogen. The Kings-B agar plates were prepared and under aseptic condition membrane filter (0.2 μ) was placed in the center of Petri plate this membrane filter was inoculated with test culture and

incubated for 48 hrs at 28±2°C. After incubation aseptically the membrane filter with the growth of test culture was removed and at the same place a disc (4mm) of actively growing phytopathogen was placed on kings-B agar plates. Plates were reincubated at 25±°C for a week along with negative control. Results were observed after every 24 hrs in term of growth of phytopathogen on Kings-B medium and the negative control and % inhibition was calculated, according to the method of Dennis and Webster (11)

4. Antagonistic activity

Antagonistic activity was tested by dual culture method. In this method Kings B agar plates were prepared. One side on agar a test culture was inoculated while 8 mm mycellial disc of a four days old culture of fungal pathogens were placed at the opposite side of the Petri dish. Similarly a control plate was kept only with phytopathogen without bacterial antagonist. Growth of fungi was inhibited when it grew towards the bacterial colony and the inhibition zone was measured from the edge of mycellium to the bacterial colony edge according the method of Schaad *et al.*, (12).

5. Production of protease enzyme

This effect was tested according to Maurhofer *et al.* (13) Efficacy of the antagonistic bacteria isolates in production of protease was tested by streaking each bacterial isolate on Skim milk agar (SMA) on the Petri dish. The bacterial isolate that produced protease were identified by a halo zone surrounding of bacterial colony and were measured

6. Defence enzyme Catalase production

This effect was tested according to Cappuccino and Sherman, (14) for the Catalase production, cultures were grown in a Nutrient agar for 24-72 hr at 37°C and 28°C. The cultures were mixed with appropriate amount of H₂O₂ on a glass slide to observe the evolution of oxygen

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Qualitative analysis for HCN production Vasudevan *et al.*, (7) reported that, Among the other methods of biological suppression of soil borne plant pathogens production of HCN by soil bacterial biocontrol agents against soil borne pathogens is most efficient but less studied mechanism in biological control of plant diseases. In present investigation all the 9 isolates tested did not show HCN production. As Michaelis and Corpe (16) reported that in his investigation he is

failed to detect the presence of hydrogen cyanide from cultures of *P. Fluorescens* although they did find that HCN was produced by *Pseudomonas chlororaphs*, *Pseudomonas aureofaciens*. **Table No. 1**

Table No. 1 Qualitative analysis for HCN production

Sr.	Culture name	HCN production
1	NM/S1/CA	-ve
2	NM/S3/NA	-ve
3	NM/S4/NA	-ve
4	NM/S5/NA	-ve
5	NM/S6/NA	-ve
6	NM/S7/NA	-ve
7	NM/S8/NA	-ve
8	NM/R2/RA	-ve
9	NM/R3/RA	-ve

2. Qualitative analysis for volatile metabolite production. Biocontrol is one of the Indirect mechanism of plant growth promotion. Volatile compounds produced are responsible for the biocontrolling activity of the plant for fungal pathogens. In present investigation none of the culture showed volatile compound production activity (**Table No. 2**)

Table No. 2 Volatile metabolite production,

Sr.	Culture name	Volatile metabolite production
1	NM/S1/CA	-ve
2	NM/S3/NA	-ve
3	NM/S4/NA	-ve
4	NM/S5/NA	-ve
5	NM/S6/NA	-ve
6	NM/S7/NA	-ve
7	NM/S8/NA	-ve
8	NM/R2/RA	-ve
9	NM/R3/RA	-ve

3. Qualitative analysis for the Non- Volatile metabolite production against

phytopathogens *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium*. As per (Table No. 3) all cultures showed production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on phytopathogen *A. niger* whereas none of the bacterial isolates showed production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on phytopathogen *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium*. after three days of inoculation. The effect diluted after third day. Maximum inhibition showed by NM/S3/NA and minimum inhibition showed by NM/S1/CA and NM/S8/CA.

Table No. 3 Qualitative analysis for the Non-Volatile metabolite production against phytopathogens *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium* . after third day of inoculation

Culture Name	Growth of phytopathogen in cm.		
	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>Sclerotium</i>
NM/S1/CA	2.1cm	-ve	-ve
NM/S3/NA	1.5cm	-ve	-ve
NM/S4/NA	1.7cm	-ve	-ve
NM/S5/NA	1.6cm	-ve	-ve
NM/S6NA	1.8cm	-ve	-ve
NM/S7/NA	1.7cm	-ve	-ve
NM/S8/CA	2.1cm	-ve	-ve
NM/R2/RA	2.0cm	-ve	-ve
NM/R3/RA	1.8cm	-ve	-ve

Table No. 4. Inhibition percent against phytopathogens *A. niger*,

Sr.	Culture name	% Inhibition
1	NM/S1/CA	12.50 %
2	NM/S3/NA	37.50 %
3	NM/S4/NA	29.16 %
4	NM/S5/NA	33.33 %
5	NM/S6NA	25.00 %
6	NM/S7/NA	29.16 %
7	NM/S8/CA	12.50 %
8	NM/R2/RA	16.66 %
9	NM/R3/RA	25.00 %

4. Qualitative analysis for antagonistic activity against phytopathogens *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium*.

As per the (Table No. 5) antagonistic activity is shown by culture NM/R3/RA against phytopathogen *A. niger* while cultures

NM/S4/NA, NM/S5/NA, NM/R2/RA showed minimum antagonistic activity as they are touching to the culture against phytopathogen *A. flavus*. None of the culture showed antagonistic activity against *Sclerotium*.

Table No. 5 Qualitative analysis for antagonistic activity against phytopathogens

A. niger, *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium* .

Culture Name	Antagonistic Activity		
	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>Sclerotium</i>
NM/S1/C A	- ve	-ve	-ve
NM/S3/N A	- ve	-ve	-ve
NM/S4/N A	- ve	touchin g	-ve
NM/S5/N A	-ve	touchin g	-ve
NM/S6NA A	-ve	-ve	-ve
NM/S7/N A	-ve	-ve	-ve
NM/S8/C A	-ve	-ve	-ve
NM/R2/R A	-ve	touchin g	-ve
NM/R3/R A	+ ve	-ve	-ve

5. Cell wall lysing enzyme

Chernin and Chet, (17). Reported that a variety of microorganisms also exhibit hyperparasitic activity, attacking pathogens by excreting cell wall hydrolases. Bashan and de-Bashan, (18) reported that these hydrolases include chitinase, β -1, 3-glucanase, protease and lipase which are known to play major role in control of fungal pathogens

Qualitative analysis for Production of protease

Production of extracellular protease was tested according to Maurhofer *et al.* (13) on skim milk agar plates. Six cultures isolates NM/S1/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/R3/RA, Strongly produced protease enzyme RA. While NM/S6/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/R2/RA showed zone of clearance, around the colony on skim milk agar. (Table No. 6) Earlier Dunlap *et al.*, (19) demonstrated that biocontrol of *Pythium ultimum* in sugar beet by *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* W81 was due to the production of extracellular

protease. Also, Kamensky *et al.*, (20) found that chitinolytic activity appears less essential for controlling *S. sclerotiorum* and *B. cinerea*, by *S. plymutica* IC14 which synthesized proteases instead of chitinases.

Above facts support our result that cultures produced protease enzymes which may contributed in efficient biocontrol.

Table No 6 Qualitative analysis of cell wall lysing enzyme Protease

Sr.	Culture Name	Protease production	Zone of clearance (mm)
1	NM/S1/CA	-ve	0mm
2	NM/S3/NA	+ve	7mm
3	NM/S4/NA	+ve	10mm
4	NM/S5/NA	-ve	0mm
5	NM/S6NA	+ve	5mm
6	NM/S7/NA	+ve	16mm
7	NM/S8/CA	-ve	0mm
8	NM/R2/RA	+ve	8mm
9	NM/R3/RA	+ve	20mm

Table No7 Qualitative analysis of defence enzyme Catalase production

Sr.	Culture Name	Catalase production
1	NM/S1/CA	+ve
2	NM/S3/NA	+ve
3	NM/S4/NA	+ve
4	NM/S5/NA	+ve
5	NM/S6NA	+ve
6	NM/S7/NA	+ve
7	NM/S8/CA	+ve
8	NM/R2/RA	+ve
9	NM/R3/RA	+ve

6. Qualitive analysis for Defence enzyme Catalase production

Systemic resistance triggered in the plant by rhizobacteria is referred to as rhizobacterial mediated induced systemic resistance (ISR) reviewed by Van Loon (21). M'Piga *et al.*, (22) reported that *Pseudomonas fluorescence* could act

as strong elicitors of plant defence reaction. ISR is brought about by PGPRs though fortification of the physical and mechanical strength of the cell wall as well as changing the physiological and biochemical reactions of the host leading to the synthesis of defence chemical against the challenge pathogen. Benhamou *et al.*, (23) stated that It is well known that PGPRs induce cell wall structural modification in response to pathogenic attack. Anderson and Guerra, (24) reported that, enhanced lignification have been reported in plants following treatments with PGPR strains. However, there is not much study about induction of various defence enzymes involved. The present study dealt with the induction of PGPR mediated defence enzymes Catalase. Induced enzyme activities by NM/S1/CA, NM/S3/NA, NM/S4/NA, NM/S5/NA, NM/S6/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/S8/CA, NM/R2/RA and NM/R3/RA may be associated with the bio-synthesis of phenolic compounds and lignin that have been considered as major determinants in inducing systemic resistance against the root rot disease.

CONCLUSION

While studying indirect mechanism of plant growth promotion, all cultures showed production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on phytopathogen *A. niger* whereas none of the bacterial isolates showed production of the non-volatile diffusible metabolite having inhibiting effect on phytopathogen *A. flavus* and *Sclerotium*. After three days of inoculation. The effect diluted after third day. Maximum inhibition showed by NM/S3/NA and minimum inhibition showed by NM/S1/CA and NM/S8/CA. Antagonistic activity is shown by culture NM/R3/RA against phytopathogen *A. niger* while cultures NM/S4/NA, NM/S5/NA, NM/R2/RA showed minimum antagonistic activity as they are touching to the culture against phytopathogen *A. flavus*. None of the culture showed antagonistic activity against *Sclerotium*. The present study dealt with the induction of PGPR mediated defence enzymes Catalase. Induced enzyme activities by NM/S1/CA, NM/S3/NA, NM/S4/NA, NM/S5/NA, NM/S6/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/S8/CA, NM/R2/RA and NM/R3/RA may be associated with the bio-synthesis of phenolic compounds and lignin that have been considered as major determinants in inducing systemic resistance against the root rot disease. Six cultures isolates NM/S1/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/R3/RA, Strongly produced

protease enzyme. While NM/S6/NA, NM/S7/NA, NM/R2/RA showed zone of clearance, around the colony on skim milk agar, which may contribute for the biocontrol against the phytopathogen.

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